

Comparison of gene expression changes in bread wheat varieties with different susceptibilities to heat stress

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Received: May 02, 2023; Reviewed: June 13, 2023; Accepted: June 20, 2023

Temperature changes negatively affect the growth and productivity of plants. The expression of the HSP 16.9 heat shock protein and DREB transcription factor genes, as well as the transcript levels of ascorbate peroxidase and glutathione peroxidase enzymes, the main enzymes of the antioxidant defense system, were studied in leaves of bread wheat genotypes with contrasting heat-sensitivity that had been exposed to short-term heat stress. Expression analysis was performed by semi-quantitative RT-PCR method and the elongation factor gene (*Elf1- α*) was used as an internal control. The expression of the HSP 16.9 gene was upregulated in all studied genotypes under high-temperature stress. The analysis of the expression profiles of antioxidant enzyme genes showed an increase in the transcriptional expression of APX and GPX in tolerant genotypes and a decrease in sensitive genotypes compared to the control. Under short-term heat stress, DREB gene expression increased in tolerant genotypes as well as in one of the sensitive genotypes. The obtained results can be useful for the initial selection of wheat genotypes for tolerance to temperature stress.

Keywords: *Triticum aestivum* L., RT-PCR, HSP 16.9, DREB, APX, GPX

INTRODUCTION

Global climate change is expected to directly affect crop production worldwide. In particular, the wheat plant is very sensitive to heat stress, and according to estimates, global wheat yields are predicted to decrease by 4%-8.5% with rising temperatures (Pandey et al., 2023). Among the abiotic stress factors, heat stress is known to lead to some morphological, physiological, and biochemical changes in the plant, which are based on the processes occurring at the level of expression of the responsible genes.

The effect of heat on the plant depends on the duration of the high temperature and the stage of the plant's development. The optimum temperature for flowering and grain-filling of the wheat plant is 12°C – 22 °C. An increase in temperature by 1-2°C during the grain-filling stage of ontogenesis shortens this period, which causes a decrease in the mass of the grain. In addition, the effect of high temperature (>35 °C) for a short period of time significantly reduces productivity (Girousse, 2023). In general, heat stress affects any developmental stage, the embryonic stage, early stages of meiosis, development of microspore and pollen cells during initiation of flowering, grain filling, root

development, etc. ultimately leading to reduced productivity (Ru et al., 2023).

Heat stress disrupts protein synthesis and folding processes. This, in turn, leads to the synthesis and accumulation of stress agents, which directly disrupt the basic metabolic processes of the cell, including DNA replication, mRNA transcription, transport, and translation. Besides, high temperatures can lead to changes in membrane potential (depolarization), lipid peroxidation, protein oxidation, and nucleic acid damage. It has been established that mild thermal treatment for a long time stimulates the physiological aging process in the plant. In contrast, a short period of very high temperature leads to denaturation and aggregation of proteins in the plant, which leads to rapid plant death (Pandey et al., 2023).

Heat-induced reactive oxygen species such as singlet oxygen (1O_2), superoxide ($O_2^{\cdot-}$), and hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot OH$) must be immediately neutralized by the antioxidant defense system to protect the plant from oxidative stress (Sachdev et al., 2021). In this regard, the activities of antioxidant enzymes, including ascorbate peroxidase (APX), catalase (CAT), glutathione reductase (GR), glutathione peroxidase (GPX), superoxide dismutase (SOD), etc. increase during

heat stress. To eliminate accumulated ROS and maintain stable metabolic activity and productivity, a whole defense system consisting mainly of transcription factors, heat shock proteins – HSPs, and antioxidant defense components operates in the plant (Mohi-Ud-Din et al., 2021). Heat shock proteins act as molecular chaperones and protect plants from heat stress by keeping the functional conformation of proteins stable. In general, 753 *TaHSP* heat shock proteins have been identified in the wheat genome, including 169 *TaSHSP*, 273 *TaHSP40*, 95 *TaHSP60*, 114 *TaHSP70*, 18 *TaHSP90*, and 84 *TaHSP100* (Kumar et al., 2020). Furthermore, these HSPs exhibit tissue specificity and developmental stage-specific expression, and upon heat stress, these shock proteins are rapidly induced by heat stress-specific transcription factors. Transcription factors belonging to regulatory proteins interact with cis-elements present in the promoter parts of various genes under abiotic stress (Manzoor et al., 2021). This effect stimulates the gene cascade, increasing the expression of many genes, resulting in the formation of tolerance against abiotic stresses. DREB (Dehydration Element Binding Factor) transcription factors are members of the AP2/ERF superfamily of plant transcription factors and are characterized by involvement in many stresses, including heat, drought, salinity, etc. (Niu et al., 2020).

Although wheat has been recognized as one of the most strategic food crops in the world, information on heat stress-induced processes in wheat, including heat shock proteins, is very limited. The effects of heat stress on the germination stage of wheat have not been fully studied. In particular, the expression of heat-related genes in wheat seedlings is one of the least studied issues. In this regard, the study of the impact of global warming on plants, including bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), which is an important food plant, is an actual problem. We aimed to perform a comparative analysis of changes induced by a short-term high temperature in the gene expression of heat shock protein HSP 16.9 and the main enzymes of the antioxidant defense system, APX and GPX, in bread wheat genotypes with different sensitivities to heat stress.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material and growing conditions.

Murov 2 and Zirva 85 genotypes, tolerant to abiotic stress factors, and Aran and Gyzyl bugda, stress-sensitive genotypes were selected from the wheat Gene Fund of the Research Institute of Crop Husbandry, Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic

of Azerbaijan. To increase the reliability of the expression analysis, the experiments were conducted in randomized complete blocks, in 2 variants, 10 biological and 3 technical replicates. The plants were grown in an artificial climate chamber with a light/dark period of 16/8 hours and 24°C/18°C day/night temperature regime, relative humidity of 50%, in individual plastic cups, in a soil-sand mixture (1/3 ratio) and 14-day-old seedlings were exposed to stress. Heat stress was created in the laboratory in a thermostat at 38°C – 30 min, 40°C – 30 min, 42°C – 2 hours.

Extraction of RNA and synthesis of cDNA:

0.2 g of leaf samples were taken from control and stressed plants and ground in liquid nitrogen, transferred to sterile 2.0 ml. Eppendorf tubes and placed in a refrigerator at -80°C. Monarch Total RNA Miniprep Kit (New England Biolabs, Inc.) was used to extract total RNA from leaf material. LunaScript RT SuperMix Kit (New England Biolabs, Inc.) was used to synthesize cDNA on total RNA. The extracted RNAs were qualitatively determined by electrophoresis on a 1% agarose gel, and their purity and concentration were measured on a NanoDrop spectrophotometer.

PCR analysis. The annealing temperature of each primer was determined by applying gradient PCR to its site. The 25 µl incubation buffer used for the DNA amplification contained 10x buffer, 20 ng of cDNA, 0.2 µM primer, 200 µM each of dATP, dCTP, dGTP and dTTP, 2.5 mM MgCl₂, and 0.2 units of Taq-polymerase. PCR was performed in an Applied Biosystems 2720 Thermal Cycler amplifier under the following conditions: cycle 1 – 4 min at 94°C; cycle 35 – 1 min at 94°C, 1 min at 60°C, 1 min at 72°C; A complementary elongation cycle was performed at 72°C for 15 min; amplification products were stored at 4°C.

Gel-electrophoresis and gel documentation:

Reaction products were clarified by conducting electrophoresis on a horizontal gel-electrophoresis (HR-2025-High Resolution (IBI SCIENTIFIC, USA)) apparatus. For this purpose, a 1.5% agarose gel, TAE 1X ((50 X):0.04 M Tris-acetate, 0.002 M EDTA) and TBE 1X (Tris 90 mM, Borate 90 mM, EDTA 2.5 mM, pH 8, 3) electrophoresis buffers were used. Images of agarose gels stained in ethidium bromide solution were documented in a special gel documentation system (Gel Documentation System «UVITEK», UK) using ultraviolet light.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Significant changes were detected in the transcript levels of the HSP 16.9 heat shock protein

and the main enzymes of the antioxidant defense system, ascorbate peroxidase and glutathione peroxidase in bread wheat leaves exposed to heat stress compared to control plants. The elongation factor gene (*Elf1- α*) was used as an internal control in the expression analysis and it was visualized in electrophoretic profiles as 200 bp fragments synthesized with the same intensity in all genotypes. The expression of the HSP 16.9 gene was intensified in all studied genotypes under short-term high-temperature stress (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Expression profile of the HSP 16.9 gene under high temperature: 1– Gyzył bugda (control), 2–Gyzył bugda (stress), 3–Murov 2 (control), 4 – Murov 2 (stress), 5 – Zirva 85 (control), 6 – Zirva 85 (stress), 7 – Aran (control), 8 – Aran (stress).

In general, interest in the study of heat shock proteins in plants is high, nevertheless lack of information about the role of these proteins in the development of heat tolerance.

In the transgenic *Arabidopsis* plants overexpressing the HSP16.9 gene, high tolerance to adverse conditions during heat shock was observed, indicating that these proteins play a key role in the formation of heat tolerance (Mu et al., 2013). The HSP16.9 protein plays a key role in the formation of heat tolerance in living organisms through chaperone activity (Basha et al., 2004). *Escherichia coli* cells producing HSP 16.9 showed high survival when the total denatured protein was reduced up to 50% (Yeh et al., 1997). According to other researchers, in the *Arabidopsis* plant, the expression of proteins such as HSP17.6, HSP70, and HSP101 increases at 37°C, while the synthesis of these proteins is completely inhibited at 39°C (Babbar et al., 2023). In the *Aloe vera* (L.) plant, a positive correlation was observed between the increase in temperature and the expression of proteins such as HSP70, HSP100, and ubiquitin (Huerta et al., 2013).

Under short-term heat stress, the expression of the DREB transcription factor gene increased in the Gyzył bugda, Murov 2, and Zirva 85 genotypes, and decreased in the Aran genotype (Figure 2). Adaptation of plants to stress conditions

implemented by the coordinated expression of entire gene ensembles requires the realization of complex genetic programs. Currently, intensive research is being conducted worldwide to identify the transcription factors involved in the stress-specific regulation of genes.

Transcription factors belonging to regulatory proteins interact with cis-elements present in the promoter parts of various genes related to abiotic stress. This effect stimulates the gene cascade, increasing the expression of many genes, resulting in tolerance to abiotic stresses. The expression of DREB genes under different abiotic stresses was extensively studied in a genetically wide variety of plant species (Niu et al., 2020).

Fig. 2. Expression profile of the DREB transcription factor gene under heat stress: 1 – Gyzył bugda (control), 2 – Gyzył bugda (stress), 3 – Murov 2 (control), 4 – Murov 2 (stress), 5 – Zirva 85 (control), 6 – Zirva 85 (stress), 7 – Aran (control), 8 – Aran (stress).

Fig. 3. Expression profiles of APX, GPX, and ELF1- α genes under heat stress: – Gyzył bugda (control), 2 – Gyzył bugda (stress), 3 – Murov 2 (control), 4 – Murov 2 (stress), 5 – Zirva 85 (control), 6 – Zirva 85 (stress), 7 – Aran (control), 8 – Aran (stress).

The analysis of the expression profiles of

antioxidant enzyme genes showed that the accumulation of APX enzyme transcripts increased in the Gyzył bugħda, Murov 2, and Zirva 85 genotypes, and decreased in the Aran genotype. The expression of GPX at the transcriptional level relatively increased in the Murov 2 and Zirva 85 genotypes compared to the control, while it was weakened in the Gyzył bugħda and Aran genotypes, which are considered sensitive genotypes (Figure 3).

The activity of various antioxidant enzymes is sensitive to temperature and their activation occurs in different temperature ranges. The activity of enzymes also depends on whether the grain culture is tolerant or sensitive, and on the vegetation stage (Chaudhary, 2020). Studies showed that SOD, APX, CAT, GPX, and GR decreased the effect of heat stress in the wheat plant (Caverzan et al., 2016). Many researchers observed an increase in the activity of antioxidant enzymes under high temperatures. There are also studies showing that an increase in temperature during the grain-filling stage in wheat plants results in a decrease in the activity of antioxidant enzymes (Liu et al., 2006). Almeselmani and colleagues (Almeselmani et al., 2009) suggest that the decrease in the activity of antioxidant enzymes may occur due to the sensitivity of the plant to heat stress. Genotypes that are tolerant to heat at the germination stage showed high productivity after treatment with high temperatures. Thus, they concluded that the initial selection for heat response can be effective in the selection for tolerance (Ru et al., 2023). The study of changes in gene expression under heat stress is important for understanding the mechanisms of plant tolerance to extreme temperatures.

CONCLUSION

Heat tolerance is a complex quantitative trait controlled by multiple genes and is vulnerable to environmental factors making the traditional breeding process of thermotolerant wheat varieties difficult. Besides, there are few direct and stable evaluation indicators and no evaluation index systems exist. Therefore, molecular biology methods are preferred to clarify the networks within the plant heat stress responses. Breeding new thermotolerant wheat varieties through genetic engineering will contribute to coping with the yield loss and poor quality caused by high temperatures and heat waves. Gene expression of the HSP 16.9 heat shock protein, the DREB transcription factor and antioxidant enzymes ascorbate peroxidase and glutathione peroxidase were studied at transcript levels in leaves of bread wheat genotypes exposed to short-term heat stress. The obtained results can

be useful for the initial selection of wheat genotypes for tolerance to temperature stress.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was implemented with the financial support of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences (Order No. 342, August 20, 2020) and the Science Development Foundation under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan (Grant No. EIF-ETL-2020-2(36)-16/15/3-M-15).

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İstilik stresinə qarşı müxtəlif həssaslığa malik yumşaq buğda genotiplərində gen ekspressiyasının müqayisəsi

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Temperatur faktorunun fluktuasiyası bitkilərin böyüməsinə və məhsuldarlığına neqativ təsir göstərir. Tədqiqat işində qısamüddətli istilik stresinə məruz qalmış və istiliyə həssaslığına fərqlənən yumşaq buğda yarpaqlarında HSP 16.9 istilik şoku zülalının və antioksidant müdafiə sisteminin əsas fermentlərindən olan askorbatperoksidaza ilə qlütationperoksidaza fermentlərinin transkript səviyyələrində gen ekspressiyası tədqiq edilmişdir. Ekspressiya analizləri yarımvəsfi RT-PZR metodu ilə həyata keçirilmiş və daxili kontrol olaraq elonqasiya faktoru genindən (Elf1- α) istifadə edilmişdir. Yüksək temperatur stresinin təsirindən tədqiq olunan bütün genotiplərdə HSP 16.9 geninin ekspressiyası yuxarı tənzimlənmə səviyyəsi göstərmişdir. Antioksidant ferment genlərinin ekspressiya profillərinin analizi göstərmişdir ki, APO və QPO-nun transkripsiya səviyyəsində ekspressiyası davamlı genotiplərdə kontrollu müqayisədə yuxarı tənzimlənmiş, həssas genotiplərdə isə aşağı tənzimlənmə səviyyəsi göstərmişdir. Qısa müddətli istilik stresinin təsirindən DREB geninin ekspressiyası davamlı genotiplərlə yanaşı bir həssas genotipdə də yuxarı tənzimlənmişdir. Alınan nəticələr buğda genotiplərinin temperatur stresinə qarşı davamlılığına görə ilkin seleksiyası üçün faydalı ola bilər.

Açar sözlər: *Triticum aestivum* L., RT-PZR, HSP 16.9, DREB, APO, QPO